

Deliverable D2.1

Essential Ocean Variables' Reliability, Accuracy, Uncertainty Maps V.1

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DELIVERABLE

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Deliverable Lead	ETT Sp.A. (ETT)
Authors	Beatrice Maddalena Scotto (ETT) Antonio Novellino (ETT)
Contributors	Johannes Karstensen (GEOMAR)
Reviewer	Chiara Bearzotti (DMI)

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AMOC	Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation
CMEMS-INSTAC	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service - In Situ Thematic Centre
CMIP7	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 7
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature, Depth
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ECV	Essential Climate Variable
EOV	Essential Ocean Variable
ESM	Earth System Model
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ERDDAP™	Environmental Research Division's Data Access Program
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FOO	Framework for Ocean Observing
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
HFR	High Frequency Radar
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
ICS	International Council for Science
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NVS	NERC Vocabulary Server
QA4EO	Quality Assured Data for Earth Observations
QC	Quality Control
RRR	Rolling Review of Requirements
SO	Specific Objective
SOOS	Southern Ocean Observing System
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WMO	World Meteorological Organization
WIGOS	WMO Integrated Global Observing System
WP	Work Package

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Publishable summary	4
2. Methodology: Algorithms and Procedures	7
2.1 EOVs-supporting variables	7
2.2 Data Sourcing	7
2.3 Data Density maps	11
2.4 Density Maps access and visualization	12
2.5 Code Overview	13
3. Preliminary Results	14
4. Conclusions and Future Perspectives	21
5. Contribution to the ObsSea4Clim objectives	23
6. Data generated in this Deliverable deposited in Zenodo	25
7. References	26
Annex I - Density map Code	27

1. Publishable summary

This deliverable describes the design approach for implementing the ObsSea4Clim Essential Ocean Variables' Reliability, Accuracy, Uncertainty Maps (V.1). More specifically, it presents the designed tools for evaluating the availability of in situ data and respective uncertainties for deriving specific Essential Ocean Variables.

The concept of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) was introduced by the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS), co-sponsored by WMO, IOC-UNESCO, and ICS. The ECV framework was established in 2003 as part of the Basic Climate Monitoring Principles (summarized in Bojinski et al., 2014) to identify variables that enable detecting changes in the earth's total climate system. In early 2010, the ocean-observing community adopted the analogous EOv concept after the OceanOPS'09 conference as outlined in the Framework for Ocean Observing (FOO; Lindstrom et al., 2012). Like ECVs but for the ocean, EOVs are designed to track the ocean's physical, chemical, and biological changes, contributing to climate monitoring, ecosystem management, and ocean forecast and warning. As an example, critical EOVs include those linked to ocean circulation and the distribution of and transport of heat, salt and other properties.

EOVs carry uncertainties to enable a mapping of the variable to an application area. In most cases, EOVs are derived quantities, which are estimated from other parameters known as EOv-supporting variables and parameterizations (e.g., a specific drag coefficient). In many cases the EOv-supporting variables contribute to more than one EOv, for example, observations of currents near the surface contribute to the "EOv surface current", "EOv surface heat flux", and "EOv surface ocean stress". EOVs supporting variables are collected with sensors mounted to a variety of observing platforms such as underwater gliders, mooring, Argo floats, research or container vessels, animals, etc. All platforms have their own sampling time, space, and parameter characteristics (e.g. Liblik et al. 2016), and only a combination of data from a variety of platforms provides the observational evidence needed to draw conclusions about

processes and eventual changes. The data can be used to track changes in global ocean conditions and variables such as ocean temperature, currents, waves, sea level, salinity, etc. Therefore, it is crucial to enable the merging of the parameter information across platforms and processed by different operators, which again requires transparent uncertainties of each single data point to be delivered with the data. It therefore is of interest to map where observed variables are available and accessible, and how well they are documented in terms of measurement accuracy and uncertainty which in turn determines the EOVs that can be derived from them.

These networks provide means to collect in situ data over time. At the European level the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet), a long-term initiative supported by the European Commission, integrates and harmonizes data from various sources, covering physical, chemical, biological, geological, seabed habitat, and human activity parameters. EMODnet Physics is the project pillar in charge of integrating both near real-time and delayed mode in situ observations on ocean physics and covers, among the others, temperature, salinity, sea level, currents, waves and winds which are EOVS-supporting variables. EMODnet Physics integrates European marine data with ocean observations from international programs, the GOOS networks, and beyond. EMODnet is designed to provide users with the most comprehensive collection of datasets, making it a key infrastructure for mapping the availability, accessibility, and documentation quality of EOVS-supporting variables.

In this framework, EMODnet Physics is the reference infrastructure for designing the ObsSea4Clim Essential Ocean Variables' Reliability, Accuracy, Uncertainty Maps (V.1), where the first outcome of the analysis is a map of density (the number of recording days for a given grid cell) for a selected EOVS-supporting parameter.

While the methodology is generally applicable to all the EOVS-supporting parameters available in EMODnet Physics, this deliverable describes the developed approach for temperature, salinity, and currents.

The applied methodology is also intended to provide insights for subsequent applications within ObsSea4clim work packages WP3, WP4, and WP5 and to develop an analysis of the completeness of metadata of the data collections available in EMODnet Physics.

A preliminary outcome shows that EMODnet Physics is not receiving fully described information about sensor accuracy and applied best practices. Many stakeholders cannot use in situ data due to a lack of transparency in the quality procedures applied, rather than concerns about data quality per se. These results will help define and address recommendations for data providers to enable better and more accurate EOVS mapping and analysis, thereby improving the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) provision of EOVS.

Improving the understanding of available observations for specific EOVS at a defined time and depth grids will not only improve the reliability of calculated EOVS but also extend their usefulness to a broader range of stakeholders..

A follow-up assessment will be carried out later in the project to monitor progress and developments related to this tool (D2.4).

The ability to understand and predict the ocean depends strongly on access to accurate, reliable and comprehensive datasets. Essential Ocean Variables (EOVS) form the basis of marine research, providing critical information on the ocean state. Important observations to estimate a variety of EOVS are for example ocean temperature, salinity, currents and other key parameters. However, despite significant advances in data collection and integration, issues remain in ensuring a reproducible uncertainty estimate is provided and data is accessible to these datasets.

This project addresses several of these challenges, such as insufficient spatial and temporal coverage of EOVS variables, resulting in incomplete datasets and limiting comprehensive ocean analysis. In addition, the use of different standardised quality control procedures undermines the reliability and accuracy of in situ observations. In contrast, inadequate metadata documentation, particularly with regard to sensor

accuracy, measurement uncertainty and applied best practices, creates difficulties for stakeholders relying on these data. In addition, challenges in integrating and harmonising datasets from different sources restrict efficient data discovery, access and re-use, limiting the usability of the information for broader applications.

To address these issues, this task focuses on developing density maps and uncertainty assessments for selected EOVs. This tool aims to provide a clear representation of where and when data is available, helping to identify gaps in data collection and areas for improvement. These results will help define and address recommendations for data providers to enable better and more accurate EOV mapping and analysis, thereby improving the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) provision of EOVs.

2. Methodology: Algorithms and Procedures

2.1 EOVs-supporting variables

The first version of the tool was tested with three Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), identified through feedback from a project-wide survey conducted for [Milestone MS2 - Decision on the EOVs to be used as a pilot and identification of the available datasets](#).

The selected EOV-supporting variables are surface temperature, subsurface temperature, and currents. In addition, sea salinity is included as a test variable, and was chosen based on its relevance and availability of the data.

2.2 Data Sourcing

EMODnet Physics is one of the seven domain-specific components of the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet), which provides free and unrestricted access to physical oceanographic data and data products. Through several development phases, EMODnet Physics has established itself as an operational service providing standardised, high-quality marine data in support of EU policies such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, the Marine Spatial Planning Directive and the

European Green Deal. Integrated into the EMODnet Central Portal (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en>), EMODnet Physics improves the accessibility and interoperability of marine data and serves as a resource for monitoring and sustainability efforts. It also collaborates with global initiatives such as GOOS, SOOS, ICES and marine infrastructures such as CMEMS-INSTAC, PANGAEA, etc. to ensure that its data contribute to international marine observing networks and programmes. Its objectives include the further development of operational services to provide seamless access to key physical parameters, as well as international data standards and initiatives for open data and sustainability.

EMODnet Physics organizes marine data by categorizing it into three key levels: in-situ data, data collection, and products.

- In-situ data consists of time series or profiles sampled by various platforms (e.g., CTDs, tide gauges, HF radars)¹.
- Data collections are groupings of similar in-situ data harmonized using common standards (e.g., salinity or temperature datasets across multiple platforms), organized using the P33-controlled NVS vocabulary². This allows seamless integration of metadata, linking terms like “salinity” to specific parameters and features such as time series or profiles (Fig. 2.1).
- Products result from processing data into value-added outputs, such as climatologies or reanalysis datasets³.

The platform ensures harmonized metadata, interoperability, and free access to data and products through standard protocols (e.g., ERDDAP, WMS/WFS), all integrated into the EMODnet Central Portal.

¹ https://data-erddap.emodnet-physics.eu/erddap/tabledap/EP_PLATFORMS_METADATA.html and https://data-erddap.emodnet-physics.eu/erddap/tabledap/EP_PLATFORMS_METADATA_CTD.html

² <https://data-erddap.emodnet-physics.eu/erddap/search/index.html?page=1&itemsPerPage=1000&searchFor=P33>

³ <https://prod-erddap.emodnet-physics.eu/erddap/info/index.html?page=1&itemsPerPage=1000>

Fig. 2.1: P33 controlled vocabulary framework.

The data collections provide the list of the platforms and the temporal and geographical boundary information, while the full data are available in single platform data files (Fig. 2.2).

EMODnet Physics - Collection of Water Temperature (SDN:P33::WATERTEMPERATURE) variables - MultiPointsObservation - METADATA

Dataset Title: **EMODnet Physics (Dataset ID: ERD_EP_WATERTEMPERATURE_INSITU_METADATA)**
 Institution: **EMODnet Physics** (Dataset ID: ERD_EP_WATERTEMPERATURE_INSITU_METADATA)
 Information: [Summary](#) | [License](#) | [FGDC](#) | [ISO 19115](#) | [Metadata](#) | [Background](#) | [Subset](#) | [Files](#) | [Make a graph](#)

Variable	<input type="checkbox"/> Check All <input type="checkbox"/> Uncheck All	Optional Constraint #1	Optional Constraint #2	Minimum or a List of Values
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PLATFORMCODE (EMODnet Platform Code)		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> call_name (Platform Call Name)		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> latitude (degrees_north)		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	-90.0
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> longitude (degrees_east)		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	-180.0
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DataFeatureType		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> firstDateObservation (UTC)		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> lastDateObservation (UTC)		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> parameters_group_longname		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> parameters_group_P02		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> parameters (Parameters Info Parameters)		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> parameters_P01 (Parameters Info P01)		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WMO		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	2
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> BEST_PRACTICES_DOI		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DATA_DOI		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> data_owner_longname (Data Owner Name)		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> data_owner_country_code		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> data_owner_country_longname		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> data_owner_EDMO (Data Owner EDMO Code)		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	0
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> data_assembly_center_longname		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> platform_type_longname		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> platform_type_SDNL06		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> platformpage_link (Platform Page)		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> integrator_id		>= <input type="text"/>	<= <input type="text"/>	

Fig. 2.2. Water Temperature data collection. Ref:

https://data-erddap.emodnet-physics.eu/erddap/tabledap/ERD_EP_WATERTEMPERATURE_INSITU_METADATA.html

Although the start and end dates of the datasets are available, the current structure lacks detailed temporal distribution of the data, such as monthly time steps. This limitation prevents the extraction and slicing of temporal information from the available data. To overcome this limitation and develop the designed dashboard, it was necessary to develop a new dedicated dataset starting from each single platform-files data that is listed in the platforms list that is defined in the data-collection product. As anticipated, each P33 data-collection product consists of one or more P01 data

collections, whereas a P01 collection includes either timeseries data (TS_XXXX) or profiles (PR_XXXX).

With this background, the study focused on implementing the first version of the dashboard for extracting the ObsSea4Clim Essential Ocean Variables' Reliability, Accuracy, and Uncertainty Maps. It concentrated on three key parameters: temperature, salinity, and ocean currents.

The development of the dataset to extract Temperature Maps, which includes both surface and subsurface measurements, involved the integration of profiles (PR_TEMP collection), time series (TS_TEMP collection) and CTD data. This temperature dataset is based on about 140.000 platforms and over 1.5 million CTD measurements⁴.

The salinity dataset includes the TS_Psal and PR_Psal data collections as well as the CTD data. It includes data from about 9,000 platforms and over 1.5 million CTD measurements.

The current dataset consists of approximately 9,700 platforms, including data from 340 HF radar stations.

2.3 Data Density maps

For each month, the data⁵ are spatially grouped into a $1^{\circ} \times 1^{\circ}$ grid, where the density of measurements for each grid cell is calculated as the total number of measurement days during the specified period.

The aggregation can be expressed mathematically as

⁴ These figures are also reported under the EMODnet Physics quarterly report Q4.2024 (31/12/2024)

⁵ In its current setup, the code retrieves platform data in six-month intervals and processes them into monthly aggregates. This approach helps prevent errors that may occur when handling large volumes of data, which could cause the server to become unresponsive.

$$D(x, y, t) = \sum_{\text{platforms}} \sum_{\text{days in months}} 1$$

where $D(x, y, t)$ represents the density of measurements at grid point (x, y) during a given time t .

With this configuration, the density D always ranges between 0 and the number of days in a given month.

This approach provides insight into the temporal availability of data, showing how often measurements have been taken for each parameter at different locations.

To facilitate improved analysis, the datasets produced will be updated monthly with the most recent data available.

2.4 Density Maps access and visualization

The following datasets are available:

- **TEMPERATURE**

https://erddap.s4oceandata.eu/erddap/griddap/DENSITY_TEMP.html

- **SALINITY**

https://erddap.s4oceandata.eu/erddap/griddap/DENSITY_PSAL.html

- **CURRENTS**

https://erddap.s4oceandata.eu/erddap/griddap/DENSITY_EWCT_NSCT.html

The visualization interface is developed as a Google Colab Python notebook project and is designed to provide an interactive dashboard for users to assess measurement availability and data coverage across the processed parameters.

The dashboard enables users to filter data by the parameter, the geographical areas, the time intervals, and the depth.

The dashboard is already designed to include more metadata-filters to enable users to refine their data selection on the type or source of the measurement platform, such as specific buoys, ships, or stations.

2.5 Code Overview

The developed notebook "*ObsSea4Clim - Density map*" is available at the following link:

<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1IUzn9wA-WSm9oGNNT3IP3xNinFZ7DtOp#scrollTo=KeDX5bYKjSyn>.

The Python code developed for the Density Map is reported in Annex I of this document. The code is using and requires the following libraries: *NetCDF4*, *Xarray*, *Cartopy*, *Matplotlib* and *Ipywidgets*.

Figure 2.3 shows the developed dashboard interface.

The image shows a dashboard interface with several filter controls. At the top, there is a dropdown menu for "Parameter" set to "Sea temperature". Below this are four range sliders: "Min latitude" (from -90.00 to 90.00), "Max latitude" (from 90.00 to -90.00), "Min longitude" (from -180.00 to 180.00), and "Max longitude" (from 180.00 to -180.00). There are also two text input fields for "Start month" (2023-06) and "End month" (2023-07). A blue link "Show code" is positioned below the month filters. At the bottom, there are two more range sliders: "Min depth" (from 0 to 2000) and "Max depth" (from 2000 to 0).

Fig. 2.3: Dashboard filters

Once the user has set the filter configuration, the dashboard elaborates and presents the density map, with a colour code ranging from green for low density to red for high density. The colour bar indicates the number of days with available measurements.

The resulting density map visually represents where and how often measurements for the selected parameter were taken over the specified time period and geographic region.

3. Preliminary Results

As described above, the density maps provide insights into the spatial and temporal availability of temperature, salinity, and sea current data.

These maps reveal significant variability in data coverage, with specific regions and time periods showing notable gaps. The platform-agnostic approach ensures comprehensive analyses without being constrained by platform-specific limitations. These first preliminary results provide a general idea of data density, but they lack granularity in terms of platform types, sensor accuracies, and best practices.

Figure 3.1 illustrates the results for the temperature variable across the entire domain during a six-month interval, from June 2024 to November 2024, encompassing all available depths.

The map represents the number of days with recorded measurements within this timeframe.

Fig. 3.1: Number of days with measurement for the Temperature over an interval of 6 months → 183 days.

Figure 3.2 shows the monthly slices of the density of the measurements.

Fig. 3.2 - Monthly measurement days for the Temperature (each sub-figure is one month from June 2024 to November 2024).

Figure 3.3 shows the density of measurements of Salinity over the same period, Figure 3.4 shows the monthly density.

Fig. 3.3 - Number of days with measurement for the Salinity over an interval of 6 months → 183 days.

Fig. 3.4: Monthly measurement days for the Salinity (each sub-figure is one month from June 2024 to November 2024).

Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.6 show the density maps for Currents.

Fig. 3.5: Number of days with measurement for the Currents over an interval of 6 months → 183 days.

Fig. 3.6: Monthly measurement days for Currents (each sub-figure is one month from June 2024 to November 2024).

4. Conclusions and Future Perspectives

This document outlines the methodology and approach to designing and developing the ObsSea4Clim dashboard for assessing EOVs' Reliability, Accessibility, and Uncertainty Maps.

The deliverable also includes preliminary results on three identified parameters that are crucial to processing EOVs. Notably, a comprehensive and thorough assessment of the densities, including uncertainties and accuracies, will be addressed in the second version of this deliverable - *D2.4 EOVs Reliability, Accuracy, Uncertainty Maps V.2* - later in the project (M42).

An essential aspect of this work is evaluating available metadata to assess data accuracy and uncertainty. The current pipeline, successfully tested on parameters such as temperature, salinity, and currents, will be reviewed and expanded to incorporate additional EOVs and platforms.

Notably, the computational requirements of this process, particularly for large datasets, are complex and a significant challenge: the processing of temperature datasets took three weeks, the salinity datasets took four weeks, and the currents took approximately one week.

Although we are considering preliminary results, the procedure already highlighted that not all platforms provide detailed metadata, particularly regarding sensor accuracy, calibration standards, and best practices.

While this first version serves as a foundation, guiding us toward the next iteration, future versions will offer more insights into the available data and the possibility of using them to extract EOVs and related products.

More specifically, this contributes to defining guidelines for including missing metadata, such as sensor specifications and accuracy, and harmonizing applied data

quality procedures. This ensures that such information is seamlessly integrated with the data when made available in key EU marine data systems and EMODnet. Being EMODnet an operational system, this means having the possibility to process EOVS related information, such as uncertainty density maps, on the fly.

The dashboard currently generates graphs that display the number of days within a given time interval during which measurements were recorded. This allows users to visually assess data density and detect any gaps in measurement availability, which can be crucial for understanding data reliability. This graphical representation is a simple yet powerful tool for stakeholders to evaluate the completeness of data and make informed decisions regarding its usage.

In line with the ObsSea4Clim DMP and Open Science practices, the developed tools and datasets are publicly available under the CC-BY license.

5. Contribution to the ObsSea4Clim objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific objectives of the project.

#SO1	<p>To develop ocean indicators, provide improved EOV/ECVs and evolve European ocean observing</p>
<p>Task 2.4 contributes significantly to developing improved EOVs and evolving European Ocean Observing Systems by providing a tool to assess the spatial and temporal coverage of different parameters. The density maps are a fundamental tool for identifying data gaps and assessing the adequacy of observing systems. The use of FAIR principles in data handling and metadata standardisation facilitates the transition from parameter-centric to EOV/ECV-centric observing systems. The dashboard provides stakeholders with an interactive tool to visualise and analyse data coverage, paving the way for the co-design of targeted indicators in future phases of the project. By laying the groundwork for improved interoperability and reliability, the deliverable directly supports the transformation of ocean observing systems to meet climate, operational and ocean health objectives.</p>	
SO2	<p>To advance the use of EOV and ECVs for improved ESM and reduced uncertainty in projections</p>
<p>Task 2.4 indirectly supports SO2 by improving the quality and availability of observational data, which are critical inputs to Earth System Models (ESMs). However, it does not directly address the development of ESMs or the reduction of uncertainties in projections. The methods and tools developed in this work, such as the quality-controlled datasets and density maps, can serve as valuable resources for constraining uncertainties and providing better validation datasets for climate models in future phases. Although not directly focused on ESM development or projections, the improved data reliability and coverage will serve as valuable inputs for future work in WP4 and WP5 aimed at reducing biases and improving process understanding in climate models.</p>	

SO3	<p>To create an interoperable data ecosystem serving multidisciplinary needs</p>
<p>By standardising the metadata and integrating the EMODnet datasets into an interoperable framework, Task 2.4 directly supports SO3. The methodologies used, including metadata harmonisation and adherence to the FAIR principles, enable seamless exchange of EOV/ECV data. The interactive visualisation tool was developed to improve accessibility for multidisciplinary stakeholders and promote use in operational services, climate monitoring and ocean health. By moving from parameter-centric to EOV/ECV-centric observations, Task 2.4 lays the foundation for the creation of an interoperable data ecosystem aligned with regional and global applications, including the European Green Deal agenda.</p>	
SO4	<p>To develop best practices and standards for interoperable in-situ and satellite observing</p>
<p>Task 2.4 contributes to SO4 by implementing robust quality control procedures, including outlier filtering, instrument drift correction, and metadata standardisation using established vocabularies such as P33. These practices enhance the reliability and interoperability of in-situ and satellite data and support the integration of multi-platform observations into coherent EOV/ECV products. The tool and methodologies are aligned with global frameworks such as QA4EO and the IOC Ocean Best Practices System, demonstrating scalability and relevance for regional and global applications. This foundational work strengthens interoperability standards and contributes to advancing best practices in ocean observing systems.</p>	
SO5	<p>To place Europe in the forefront of the global coordination of the broader ocean-climate nexus</p>

Task 2.4 supports SO5 by improving the quality, transparency and accessibility of EOVS data through tools such as density maps and interactive dashboards. These outputs enhance Europe's ability to contribute to global initiatives such as the European Digital Twin for the Ocean and the UN Decade for Ocean Science. While not directly engaging in policy dialogue, Task 2.4 provides tools and methodologies that support evidence-based decision-making and are consistent with Europe's leadership in the ocean-climate-biodiversity nexus. By ensuring compliance with global standards and interoperability, this work strengthens Europe's position in the coordination of sustainable ocean observing systems.

6. Data generated in this Deliverable deposited in Zenodo

The datasets generated as part of this Deliverable will be deposited in the [Zenodo ObsSea4Clim Community](#). Zenodo, as an OpenAIRE-compliant platform, facilitates open access and long-term preservation of research outputs. Publishing data on Zenodo ensures improved visibility and discoverability, as the platform assigns DOIs to datasets if not already available, making them easily traceable.

This initiative promotes transparency and accessibility and supports seamless integration with EMODnet by aligning with its open data principles. By depositing datasets on Zenodo, we aim to enhance collaboration within the marine science community and ensure that the data can be efficiently reused for research, policy-making, and other applications.

7. References

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Annex I - Density map Code

```
# @title
%%capture
!pip install netcdf4==1.6.4 cartopy xarray==0.20.0 numpy==1.26.4

import requests
import os
import netCDF4
import numpy as np
import cartopy.crs as ccrs
import cartopy.io.shapereader as shpreader
from matplotlib.colors import LinearSegmentedColormap
from mpl_toolkits.axes_grid1 import make_axes_locatable
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import xarray as xr
import pandas as pd
import ipywidgets as widgets
from ipywidgets import HBox, VBox
from datetime import datetime
from dateutil.relativedelta import relativedelta

params = {
    'Electrical conductivity': 'CNDC',
    'Dissolved oxygen': 'DOXY',
    'Bathymetric depth': 'BATH',
    'Total alkalinity': 'ALKW',
    'Absolute salinity': 'ASAL',
    'Sea density (sigma-theta)': 'DENS',
    'Total chlorophyll-a': 'CPHL',
    'Air temperature in dry bulb': 'DRYT',
    'Daily precipitation rate (liquid water equivalent)': 'PRRD',
    'Hourly precipitation rate (liquid water equivalent)': 'PRRT',
    'Sound velocity': 'SVEL',
    'Current to direction relative true north': 'HCDT',
    'Nitrate (no3-n)': 'NTRA',
    'Nitrite (no2-n)': 'NTIW',
    'Sea level expressed as pressure': 'PREX',
    'Radial sea water velocity away from instrument': 'RDVA',
    'Silicate (sio4-si)': 'SLCW',
    'Sea temperature from oxygen sensor': 'TEMP_DOXY',
    'Wind strength and direction': 'EWSB',
    'Gust wind speed': 'GSPD',
    'Sound pressure level at 63hz (20s integration time)': 'SPL63',
    'Bottom-top current component': 'VCSP',
    'Wave direction rel. true north': 'VDIR',
    'Average height highest 1/10 wave (h1/10)': 'VH110',
    'Spectral moments (0,2) wave period (tm02)': 'VTM02',
    'Raw current meter output parameters': 'LERR',
```

```
'Longwave/atmospheric incoming radiation': 'LINC',
'Ph at 25 \u00b0C and 0 dbar': 'PH25',
'River flow rate': 'RVFL',
'Sea temperature from tsg': 'SSJT',
'Light attenuation coefficient': 'TUR2',
'Turbidity of water in the water body': 'TUR6',
'Average height highest 1/3 wave (h1/3)': 'VAVH',
'Wave spectrum peak energy (smax)': 'VEPK',
'Beaufort wind force': 'WBFO',
'Colored dissolved organic matter': 'CDOM',
'Horizontal velocity of the water column (currents)': 'RFVL',
'Average period highest 1/3 wave (t1/3)': 'VAVT',
'Depth of the deepest trough': 'VMNL',
'Significant wave height': 'VTDH',
'Air temperature in wet bulb': 'WETT',
'Chlorophyll-a fluorescence': 'FLU2',
'Fluorescence': 'FLU3',
'Dew_point_temperature': 'DEWT',
'Currents': 'EWCT_NSCT',
'Co2 partial pressure': 'PCO2',
'Sound pressure level at 125hz (20s integration time)': 'SPL125',
'Swell direction rel true n.': 'SWDR',
'Mean wave from direction': 'THETA1',
'Wave principal direction at spectral peak': 'VPED',
'Maximum wave period (tmax)': 'VTMX',
'Wave period at spectral peak / peak period (tp)': 'VTPK',
'Surface incoming photosynthetic active radiation': 'LGH4',
'Net total incoming radiation': 'NRAD',
'Average period highest 1/10 wave (t1/10)': 'VT110',
'Hourly rainfall rate': 'HOURLY_RAIN',
'Dissolved organic nitrogen': 'NODW',
'Nitrate + nitrite': 'NTRZ',
'Dissolved oxygen (deprecated)': 'UDOX',
'Wave directional spreading at spectral peak': 'VPSP',
'Average zero crossing wave period (tz)': 'VTZA',
'Maximum zero crossing wave height (hmax)': 'VZMX',
'Direction of radial vector away from instrument': 'DRVA',
'Gust wind from direction relative true north': 'GDIR',
'Horizontal current speed': 'HCSP',
'Ph': 'PHPH',
'Total incoming radiation': 'RDIN',
'Sound pressure level (20s integration time)': 'SPL',
'Directional spread around theta2': 'STHETA2',
'Swell height': 'SWHT',
'Principal wave from direction': 'THETA2',
'Light transmission': 'TUR3',
'Generic average wave period': 'VGTA',
'Light backscattering': 'BACKSCATTERING',
'Wave direction': 'GWDR',
'Height_above_mean_sea_level': 'ALTS',
'Total chlorophyll': 'CHLT',
```

```
'Immerged incoming photosynthetic active radiation': 'LGHT',
'Phosphate (po4-p)': 'PHOW',
'Sea potential temperature': 'POTENTIAL_TEMP',
'Residual sea level (observed - predicted)': 'SLVR',
'Spectral moments (-1,0) wave period (tm-10)': 'VTM10',
'Oxygen saturation': 'OSAT',
'Practical salinity': 'PSAL',
'Sea sigma-theta': 'SIGMA_THETA',
'Swell period': 'SWPR',
'Estimated maximum wave height': 'VEMH',
'Max period highest 1/3 wave': 'VMAT',
'Period of the highest wave': 'VTZM',
'South-north wind component': 'WSPN',
'Vertical velocity of the water column (currents)': 'LRZA',
'Shortwave/solar incoming radiation': 'SINC',
'Water surface height above a specific datum': 'SLEV',
'Sound pressure level at 2khz (20s integration time)': 'SPL2k',
'Sea temperature': 'TEMP',
'Turbidity': 'TURMGL',
'Mean wave direction from (mdir)': 'VMDR',
'Height of the highest crest': 'VMXL',
'Wind from direction relative true north': 'WDIR',
'Horizontal wind speed': 'WSPD',
'Atmospheric pressure at altitude': 'ATMP',
'Atmospheric pressure at sea level': 'ATMS',
'Dissolved organic carbon': 'CORW',
'Phycobolin pigment concentrations in the water column': 'PHYC',
'Relative humidity': 'RELH',
'Maximum crest trough wave height (hc,max)': 'VCMX',
'Directional spread around theta1': 'STHETA1',
'Atmospheric pressure hourly tendency': 'ATPT',
'Number of bacteria cells in sea water': 'BCCW',
'Spectral significant wave height (hm0)': 'VHM0',
'Average zero crossing wave height (hzm)': 'VHZA',
'Spect. moment(0,2) wave period': 'VSMC',
'Wave scalar spectral density': 'VSPEC1D',
'Maximum wave steepness': 'VST1',
'Wave height and period statistics': 'WVST',
'Co2 fugacity': 'FCO2',
'Dissolved nitrogen': 'NGDW',
'Light scattering': 'SCATTERING',
'Dissolved inorganic carbon': 'TICW',
'Total suspended matter': 'TSMP',
'Generic significant wave height (hs)': 'VGHS',
'West-east wind component': 'WSPE',
'Wind to direction relative true north': 'WTODIR',
'Observed instantaneous water level': 'WLEV'
}

depth_bins={
  0: [0, 5],
```

```

    5: [5, 10],
    10: [10, 20],
    20: [20, 30],
    30: [30, 40],
    40: [40, 50],
    50: [50, 100],
    100: [100, 250],
    250: [250, 500],
    500: [500, 1000],
    1000: [1000, 1500],
    1500: [1500, 2000],
    2000: [2000, 2500],
    2500: [2500, 10000]
}
# @title

params_density_resp =
requests.get('https://erddap.s4oceandata.eu/erddap/griddap/index.json')

params_density_json = params_density_resp.json()
params_density = params_density_json['table']['rows']
params_density = [dataset[-1] for dataset in
params_density_json['table']['rows'] if 'DENSITY_' in dataset[-1]]

cleaned_params = {k: v for k, v in params.items() if v in
[p.replace('DENSITY_', '') for p in params_density]}

selected_var = None
pr_ts = None

def update_selected_param(change):
    global selected_var
    selected_var = change.new
    selected_var = cleaned_params[selected_var]

def update_selected_pr_ts(change):
    global pr_ts
    pr_ts = change.new

dropdown_param = widgets.Dropdown(
    options=cleaned_params.keys(),
    description='Parameter:',
    value= list(cleaned_params.keys())[0]
)
dropdown_param.observe(update_selected_param, names='value')

pr_ts_dropdown = widgets.Dropdown(
    options=['Time series', 'Profile', 'Both'],
    description='Type:',
)
pr_ts_dropdown.observe(update_selected_pr_ts, names='value')

```

```

min_latitude_slider = widgets.FloatSlider(value=-90, min=-90, max=90,
step=0.5, description='Min latitude:', style={'description_width':
'initial'})
max_latitude_slider = widgets.FloatSlider(value=90, min=-90, max=90,
step=0.5, description='Max latitude:', style={'description_width':
'initial'})
min_longitude_slider = widgets.FloatSlider(value=-180, min=-180, max=180,
step=0.5, description='Min longitude:', style={'description_width':
'initial'})
max_longitude_slider = widgets.FloatSlider(value=180, min=-180, max=180,
step=0.5, description='Max longitude:', style={'description_width':
'initial'})

start_time_input = widgets.Text(
    placeholder='2024-01',
    description='Start month:',
    disabled=False
)

end_time_input = widgets.Text(
    placeholder='2024-06',
    description='End month:',
    disabled=False
)

hbox_1 = HBox([dropdown_param])
hbox_2 = HBox([min_latitude_slider, max_latitude_slider])
hbox_3 = HBox([min_longitude_slider, max_longitude_slider])
hbox_4 = HBox([start_time_input, end_time_input])

vbox = VBox([hbox_1, hbox_2, hbox_3, hbox_4])
vbox

# @title
if selected_var is None:
    selected_var = list(cleaned_params.values())[0]

available_depths_resp =
requests.get(f'https://erddap.s4oceandata.eu/erddap/griddap/DENSITY_{selecte
d_var}.json?depth')

available_depths_json = available_depths_resp.json()
available_depths_mins = [d[0] for d in
available_depths_json['table']['rows']]
available_depths_maxs = [d[1] for d in depth_bins.values() if d[0] in
available_depths_mins]

min_depth_slider = widgets.SelectionSlider(
    options=available_depths_mins,
    value=available_depths_mins[0],

```

```

description='Min depth:',
disabled=False,
continuous_update=False,
orientation='horizontal',
readout=True
)
max_depth_slider = widgets.SelectionSlider(
options=available_depths_maxs,
value=available_depths_maxs[-1],
description='Max depth:',
disabled=False,
continuous_update=False,
orientation='horizontal',
readout=True
)

VBox([min_depth_slider, max_depth_slider])

# @title

min_depth = min_depth_slider.value
max_depth = max_depth_slider.value

selected_depths = [d for d in available_depths_mins if d >= min_depth and d
< max_depth]

min_lat = min_latitude_slider.value
max_lat = max_latitude_slider.value
min_lon = min_longitude_slider.value
max_lon = max_longitude_slider.value

min_time = start_time_input.value
max_time = end_time_input.value

if min_time is None or min_time == '':
    min_time = '2024-01'

if max_time is None or max_time == '':
    max_time = '2024-06'

max_time = datetime.strptime(max_time, '%Y-%m') #- relativedelta(seconds=1)
max_time_str = str(max_time - relativedelta(seconds=1))[:10]
max_time = max_time.strftime('%Y-%m-%d')

def generate_monthly_time_tuples(dt_min, dt_max):
    if relativedelta(dt_max, dt_min).months < 1 and dt_min.year ==
dt_max.year:
        return [(dt_min, dt_max)]
    times = []

```

```

    next_month_start = (dt_min + relativedelta(months=1)).replace(day=1,
hour=0, minute=0, second=0, microsecond=0)
    first_end = min(next_month_start, dt_max)
    times.append((dt_min, first_end))
    current_start = next_month_start
    while current_start < dt_max:
        next_month_start = (current_start +
relativedelta(months=1)).replace(day=1, hour=0, minute=0, second=0,
microsecond=0)
        current_end = min(next_month_start, dt_max)
        times.append((current_start, current_end))
        current_start = next_month_start
    return times

def generate_yearly_time_tuples(dt_min, dt_max):
    if dt_min is None: dt_min = datetime(1900,1,1,0,0,0)
    if dt_max is None: dt_max = datetime.now()
    if dt_min.year == dt_max.year:
        return [(dt_min, dt_max)]
    times = []
    current_start = dt_min
    while current_start < dt_max:
        year_start = current_start
        year_end = datetime(year_start.year, 12, 31, 23, 59, 59)
        year_end = min(year_end, dt_max)
        times.append((year_start, year_end))
        current_start = datetime(year_start.year + 1, 1, 1)
    return times

min_time_dt = datetime.strptime(min_time, '%Y-%m')
max_time_dt = datetime.strptime(max_time, '%Y-%m-%d')

time_tuples = generate_monthly_time_tuples(min_time_dt, max_time_dt)
time_tuples = [(t[0].strftime('%Y-%m'), t[1].strftime('%Y-%m')) for t in
time_tuples]

all_df = pd.DataFrame()

for time_tup in time_tuples:
    min_t = time_tup[0]
    max_t = time_tup[1]

    url =
f'https://erddap.s4oceandata.eu/erddap/griddap/DENSITY_{selected_var}.nc?DEN
SITY%5B({selected_depths[0]})%5D%5B({selected_depths[-1]})%5D%5B({min_t}-01)%5D%5B({max_t}-01)%5D%5B({min_lat})%5D%5B({max_lat})%5D%5B({min_lon})%5D%5B({max_lon})%5D'

    resp_netcdf = requests.get(url)

    try:

```

```

ds = xr.open_dataset(resp_netcdf.content, decode_times=False)

df = ds.to_dataframe().reset_index()
df_agg = df.groupby(['latitude',
'longitude'])['DENSITY'].max().reset_index()

if all_df.empty:
    all_df = df_agg
else:
    all_df = pd.merge(all_df, df_agg, on=['latitude', 'longitude'],
how='outer', suffixes=('_old', '_new'))
    all_df['DENSITY'] = all_df['DENSITY_old'].fillna(0) +
all_df['DENSITY_new'].fillna(0)
    all_df = all_df.drop(columns=['DENSITY_old', 'DENSITY_new'])

except Exception as e:
    print(f"Error processing data for {min_t} to {max_t}: {e}")
    print(resp_netcdf)
    print(str(resp_netcdf.content)[:200])

if not all_df.empty:

def display_map(ax, plt):
    plt.gcf().set_size_inches(16, 9)
    plt.tight_layout()
    plt.show()

def create_map(df):
    print_min_month = min_time
    print_max_month = max_time

    fig = plt.figure()
    ax = fig.add_subplot(1, 1, 1, projection=ccrs.PlateCarree())

    grid_dimension = 1
    lon_bins = np.arange(-180, 181, grid_dimension)
    lat_bins = np.arange(-90, 91, grid_dimension)

    heatmap, lon_edges, lat_edges = np.histogram2d(
        df['longitude'], df['latitude'],
        bins=[lon_bins, lat_bins],
        weights=df['DENSITY']
    )

    colors = [(0, '#ffffff'), (0.0000000001, '#238823'), (0.5,
'#FFBF00'), (1, '#D2222D')]
    custom_cmap = LinearSegmentedColormap.from_list('custom_colormap',
colors)
    pcm = ax.pcolormesh(lon_edges, lat_edges, heatmap.T,
cmap=custom_cmap, transform=ccrs.PlateCarree())
    
```

```

        shpfilename = shpreader.natural_earth(resolution='10m',
category='physical', name='land')
        reader = shpreader.Reader(shpfilename)
        land_geoms = list(reader.geometries())
        ax.add_geometries(land_geoms, ccrs.PlateCarree(),
facecolor='darkgrey')
        ax.coastlines()

        ax.set_extent([min_lon, max_lon, min_lat, max_lat],
crs=ccrs.PlateCarree())
        cbar = ax.figure.colorbar(pcm, ax=ax, orientation='vertical',
fraction=0.023, pad=0.041)
        cbar.set_label('N of days with measurements')

        depth_range = str(min_depth) + '-' + str(max_depth)
        ax.set_title(f'Number of days with {selected_var} data from
{min_time}-01 to {max_time_str} at depths {depth_range} m')

        return ax, plt
    ax, plt = create_map(all_df)
    display_map(ax, plt)
else:
    print('No available data for the selected time range')

```